

Higher Education In Paulo Freire's Critical Pedagogy: Commitment To Democratic Social Morality

Younis Fared Abu Alhaija

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Higher Education, Critical Pedagogy, Paulo Freire, Democratic Education, Social Change</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5110456</p>	<p><i>This article aims to investigate the issue of higher education in Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy. This pedagogy harshly criticizes the traditional professional function that characterizes the mission of higher education institutions and sees them as a major arena for professional training that realizes the economic interests of the hegemonic group. In addition, these institutions have become an instrument for training potential employees to pursue purely economic interests, thus becoming a major tool that serves, in great loyalty, the capitalist agenda. Against this reality, Freire's critical pedagogy sees academic education as a kind of humanist mission and emphasizes that higher education institutions are committed to a democratic social morality that allows the learning community not only to understand the social reality and human social dilemmas that exist in society alone, but to become critical and social activists and work for the realization of a comprehensive social transformation. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to examine the alternative that this pedagogy poses for creating a new moral and humanistic space that strives to shape a more reformed and democratic society.</i></p>

Introduction

Critical pedagogy criticizes very harshly towards higher modern education. Various thinkers argue that the crisis of modernity poses difficult challenges to the humanistic conception of modern higher education (Gur-Ze'ev, 2004: 111). The concrete modern reality, from the point of view of critical pedagogy, is largely influenced by the capitalist agenda which has transformed the status of higher education into an instrument that serves the economic, political and cultural interests of capitalism (Mourad, 1997:79). The capitalist agenda, as Gur-Ze'ev argues, not only ignores concrete educational needs but purports to subordinate higher education along with intellectuals to market logic (Gur-Ze'ev, 2004: 110). This reality brought about a fundamental change in the nature of higher education and that the tradition of objective and universal reason that characterized the academic ideal was repelled from the economic and social technological reality (Gur-Ze'ev, 1999: 304). Apart from this, the value of the academic work is estimated not from the metaphysical perspective and the pretension to truth but according to the degree of contribution to technological progress and the pretension to 'practical' efficiency and usefulness in the social space of the hegemonic group. This reality led to a considerable depletion of the status of the knowledge produced in the academic space, and at the same time the social status of the academics also began to change. The ideal of the educated person as a sage and as having moral responsibility, is converted into the ideal of the professional, the 'expert' (Gur-Ze'ev, 2004: 115). The fiancé and passion for humanistic academic education through the human sublimation that includes nurturing human values along with the forefront of free knowledge and creativity, were defeated and even became enslaved by the forces of the market and the logic of technology culture. Attempts to industrialize academia and subject it to market logic undermines the democratic potential of academic education, the nature of scientific advancement, and threaten the conditions for the possibility of a general cultural flourishing in contemporary society. It is true that this is a danger of the dissolution of academic values and a contribution to the disintegration of an intellectual, critical and creative perspective that has enabled the crystallization of modernization and the shaping of a liberal democratic horizon (Gur-Zeev et al., 2007: 58).

In the face of this reality and especially in the face of criticism of the inability of higher education to meet the challenges posed by the capitalist agenda, various critical pedagogies have emerged including the critical pedagogy of Paulo Freire. This pedagogy refuses to accept the principle of market forces and the logic of technology culture and challenge the challenges posed by this agenda. The article aims to identify and clarify the challenges that the capitalist agenda poses to modern higher education and its goals and at the same time, to examine the alternative that the critical pedagogy of Freire poses against this agenda. Hence, a number of questions arise that will be posed to us in this article: What are the challenges that the capitalist agenda poses to modern higher education? To what extent did the capitalist agenda influence the designation and role of modern

higher education? What is the alternative that Freire's critical pedagogy pits against this agenda and what is it for?

Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy

Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy is perceived as a partner in critical pedagogy for many reasons, including the principle of refusal. However, this pedagogy differs from the other pedagogies in that it is not only satisfied with refusal, but also incorporates the principle of hope and presents an optimistic pedagogy that has aspirations for socio-political liberation (Shull, 1968: 10-12).

The universal human conception presented by Freire stems from the conception of the process of liberation as a process of humanization. According to Ferreira, anyone can break free from the shackles of dehumanization, it is an important element in the optimistic component of pedagogy. According to the basic premise of this pedagogy, there is no absolute historical fact that person cannot change. History and reality are shaped by human beings and allow them a degree of humanization or dehumanization. This perception emphasizes, therefore, the historical fact that assumes that person is capable of realizing his human destiny within the context of a humane society. The existence of a humane context gives a human the possibility of controlling his life and in general, the possibility of realizing his humanity within this context (Freire, 1970: 31-35).

Another basic premise in Freire's critical pedagogy, which is perceived as an essential principle and even a necessary condition for the realization of a universal humanity and its integrity, is freedom. Freedom is perceived by Freire as of great importance which enables a person to realize his human destiny and inevitably leads to the recognition that this right, the right to be human, applies to all human beings. The recognition of this right, allows a person to fight for a change in the given objective reality and to create a new situation that allows the search for a more complete humanity (Freire, 1985: 82). However, Freire emphasizes that in the absence of freedom, the individual is deprived of the possibility of realizing his human wholeness and thus, the mechanisms of reproduction are given, within the socio-political context, to oppress the individual and lead to dehumanization that distorts his world and even his humanity. This situation leads to the loss of the individual's ability to shape his identity and leads to the limitation of his level of consciousness, and the enslavement of his will within the ideological context which serves the interests of the ruling hegemony (Freire, 1974: 5; Apple, 2012).

Because the source of hope for the liberation and humanization of the context is not in political revolutions, but in human consciousness, education has become a central component in the possibility of its realization. This led Freire's critical pedagogy to propose a transformation to education itself: from the agent of normalization to the agent of hope (Freire, 1970: 68-73). At the same time, Freire declares the importance of the existence of a critical consciousness among human beings as to the oppressive reality, as a necessary condition for the realization of their human destiny. That is, in order to realize universal human emancipation, human beings must be equipped with the means necessary to ensure this belief. This process requires wholeness in thought and action together, and involvement in the struggle for liberation and full humanization.

Paulo Freire's radical educational conception

Freire was recognized as the first thinker of the radical movement in education. His pedagogical approach emphasizes that education cannot be treated as a neutral or detached issue from political, social and economic contexts but is perceived as a political act (Shore, 2000: 1). Freire emphasizes the insight that education is a political practice, which concerned the control of language and consciousness, as a condition for the control of the world of groups and individuals by hegemonic groups. Therefore, Freire sees education as one of the main mechanisms that society uses to enslave and oppress the individual. According to Freire, education is a "reproducing" agent for the existing political, social and economic construction in society and thus, it gives society the legalization to shape the identity and personality of the individual according to its needs, and the ideology that serves its interests (Freire & Macedo, 1995).

There are no schools at all and teachers in particular are allowed to have a discourse of a political nature within the content taught that will allow them to question or doubt the status quo (Freire, 1970: 60; Apple, 2012). The existence of an educational system devoid of politics and critical thinking leads to the formation of obedient, impotent beings who succumb to the fact of oppression and are unable to challenge social conventions and in general, bring about a transformation of the normalizing socio-political context. This reality, as Freire argues, is an outgrowth of the school education system called the "banking" approach in education (Scapp, 2016). This approach turns students into passive objects and worthless objects and in general, brings them into a state of surrender and adaptation to the given objective reality and the destruction of their creative ability to change the given reality in which they find themselves and thus perpetuates the status quo and existing reality: unshakable objective reality (Freire & Shor, 1987).

Paulo Freire's liberating pedagogy

As an alternative to the "banking" education that prevails among various educational institutions, including academia, Freire presents us with a liberating education that is not only intended to develop the subject's critical awareness, but links the development of critical awareness in his future action for liberation (Freire, 1970: 41). In other words, Freire argues that the individual's thinking ability is a means of carrying out the act of liberating humanity, when doing involves thinking. Freire's liberating education strives for social change but is aware that education itself does not play an active role in the process of transformation. The role of education is reflected in the development of students' awareness of the forces at work in the social context and in stimulating critical awareness in order to become autonomous in their decisions and masters of their own destiny (Scapp, 2016). At the same time, if human beings remain passive and do not take an active part in activities for the realization of change, education will become a political preacher and tool of oppression that removes responsibility from the subject and transfers it to external forces (Cohen, 1983: 184). In this spirit it can be said that the doing is perceived as the right of existence of the oppressed who is released, however, this doing has no real existence without consciousness and without deep thought. Hence, there is an inseparable dependence between the doing and the critical thought in which only the true praxis takes place (Freire, 1970: 21). In other words, the ability of the oppressed to attain autonomy is realized only through a combination of thought and action.

In the liberating radical education of Freire, dialogical education is given a privileged status as it strives to bring human beings to critically understand the reality in which they are given and not to understand it intermittently, but to grasp the whole (Halabi, 2019: 128). Dialogue is considered the way in which human beings give meaning to their world and therefore, it is an existential necessity. In its application in the educational process, dialogue is the counter method to the control relations and modes of authority accepted in mass education (Mercer & Littleton, 2007). The dialogue in Freire is an expression of political ideology, and it states that the source of learning cannot be the result of the teacher's initiative alone, but dialogue between teachers and students in setting learning goals and the learning process (Gover, 1990: 8). Hence, the dual role of dialogue can be discerned: on the one hand, it is an antidote that expresses Freire's criticism of banking education and, on the other hand, it is an educational-political tool. As an educational-political means, critical dialogue prepares students for life in a democratic and egalitarian society and therefore, from Freire's point of view, there is no oppressors and oppressed in dialogue, but rather a dialogue between equals.

Higher education in Paulo Freire's critical Pedagogy

Similar to the harsh criticism against normalized hegemonic education, Freire goes against the academic institutions for becoming an instrument for training potential employees to pursue only economic interests, and thus becoming a major tool that serves, in great loyalty, the economic interests of the ruling group (Biren, 2003: 165; De Malach, 2008; Hayosh & Shmuelevich, 2019). As a result, Freire developed an educational-social approach based on an analysis of the socio-political reality of the learners. This approach dealt with the processes of liberation and empowerment by connecting learners to the extensive knowledge and reading, analyzing and understanding the realities of their lives. Freire's pedagogy strives to realize a liberating political force that can lead to a change in reality that promotes forms of social oppression and exploitation (McLaren, 1997: 69-70). Freire sharply criticizes and even expresses his opposition to the curricula that exist in the various education systems and especially the university. Freire's opposition stems from the fact that these programs do not deal with the analysis of problematic social issues such as inequality, injustice, oppression and discrimination, etc., but provide professional training only for students and thus prevent learners from discussing and analyzing the socio-political reality that led to insane society (Freire, 1970: 17).

This reality, as Freire argues, primarily serves the interests of the hegemonic-capitalist group in that it shapes a static and impotent personality and prevents the existence of what is called a "critical consciousness" among intellectuals. This helps the hegemonic group to maintain the status quo and in general, to preserve the unequal power structure that exists within society (Shore, 2000: 12). In addition to professional training, as Freire claims, higher education should embody and produce the necessary conditions that enable students to understand the nature and manner of ideologies that led to the creation of struggles and conflicts between different peoples within society (Macedo, 1995: 389). Freire's critical pedagogy offers alternatives to more egalitarian educational endeavors and gives marginalized populations the opportunity to challenge the hegemonic structure that hid their voices and in general, allows them to create a fundamental change in their lives. Freire sees academic education as a kind of humanist mission that enables these populations to be conscious. That is, to know their world and the special conditions that led to its formation. This educational approach gives the student the ability to think critically and act, within his world, as a subject of history and not as an object shaped according to the views of the hegemonic group (Freire, 1987: 23). In order to realize this concept, Ferreira attaches great importance to the intellectual and sees it as a major means of changing reality. Why? According to Freire, the intellectual has the ability to develop and empower students by imparting the knowledge and social skills they need to function as critical agents in a wider society towards a transformative act (Giroux, 1997). In other words, Freire emphasizes the need to educate and train students to fight for the realization of institutional change and to struggle against repression and for a more democratic society.

Intellectual activity, according to Ferreira, is a reference to the problems of life, society and the world. It is thus the political nature of intellectual activity (Cushman, 1999: 335). The intellectual as a "reality changer" must anchor teaching and learning and must believe in his ability to offer possibilities of social liberation. The role of the intellectual is to make pedagogy more political and politics more educational. Intellectuals have the ability to combine reflection and action for the empowerment of students and to be a kind of critical player who is committed to developing a world free from oppression and exploitation. Intellectuals not only focus on promoting students' individual achievements but rather, attach great importance to the process of empowering students which will enable them to read, critically, the world and work for change if necessary (Aronowitz & Giroux, 1985: 36).

Another principle that is perceived as of great importance in higher education is the "dialogue". According to Freire, dialogue is a way of creating a discourse that includes respect for culture and the person, hope for liberation and even love that embodies the belief in each person's ability to learn (Aloni, 2008). Freire emphasized the importance of critical dialogue in academia and believed that it contributes to students' personal development and growth, enabling them both to present social criticism stemming from observing reality, and to create social change (Freire, 1970: 61). The work of teachers (as intellectuals) with students, from Freire's view, must be ideological work, requiring a broad social vision, an understanding of their social mission and a desire to create social change through education.

Higher education and commitment to social democratic morality

The Freirean approach sees higher education institutions as a primary arena for professional training that realizes the economic interests of the ruling group (Dobrin, 2015; Hayosh & Shmuelevich, 2019: 97). Freire harshly criticizes the traditional professional function that characterizes the vocation of higher education and argues that democratic education is the most appropriate function for higher education. Therefore, Freire sees that such institutions are committed to a democratic social morality that allows students not only to understand the social reality and human social dilemmas that exist in society only, but to become social activists and work for overall social transformation (Biren, 2003: 166).

Freire goes against the perception that is prevalent in institutions of higher learning that knowledge is deposited in the minds of passive students and claims that it is a model of an oppressive hierarchical structure that makes the student a victim of the system (Rocha, 2006: 3). Instead, Freire calls on these institutions to adopt the model of a democratic structure in which there is a democratic relationship between them and the students (Freire, 2005: 111). In his view, this model is a realization of a democratic ideal within higher education institutions which is reflected in the motivation of students to be more critical and to act responsibly for world change. The critical aspect of higher education, plays a significant role in shaping the personality of the learning community (GurZiv, 2013). Democratic education, within the framework of higher education, can give the learning community great power and power to create a new moral and humanistic space that strives to shape a more just and democratic society. Hence, critique is necessary for the realization of social and humanistic transformation. This function plays an important role in the lives of citizens and enables them to re-examine the militant power and ability needed to overcome the forces influencing the reality in which they find themselves.

In this way, he realizes the idea of liberation that underlies Freire's revolutionary proposal (Rocha, 2006: 4). To realize this destiny, as Freire argues, academia must remain neutral and apolitical. The unique mission of higher education institutions is reflected in the shaping of a critical intellectual personality that has the power and strength needed to challenge the forces influencing the existing reality. These institutions are not a political instrument in the hands of the dominant hegemony for the realization of political and economic interests, but are perceived as a moral and humanistic means aimed at exposing the means of oppression that the hegemony uses to ensure its continued control within society (Torres, 1998: 245). In this spirit, higher education becomes privileged, striving to produce a just and democratic society through the critical and necessary involvement of talented intellectuals to be democratic and activist citizens and to work for a civil-democratic and multicultural society.

Freire emphasizes that the mission of universities should focus on training graduates with social skills and turning them into social activists who can work for the creating of a solidary, reconciled and reformed society. In this context, he seeks to convert the character of universities, from institutions designed for professional training to institutions of a democratic social nature. Such institutions enable students not only to understand the social reality and human social dilemmas that exist in society, but to train them to be transformative democratic agents (Biren, 2003: 166). In addition, Freire emphasizes that it is the responsibility of universities to provide unique opportunities for the learning community to develop high thinking skills, such as skills of strengthening relationships with the "other" and "different", critical inquiry, and training them to engage in social activities toward realizing pluralistic democracy. Moreover, Ferreira emphasizes that higher education institutions must adopt dialogue in the process of training the learning community. In his opinion, the existence of a critical dialogue in the training process, not only allows learners to respect knowledge, respect only different perspectives, but allows them to examine the unequal power relations, reveal the voices that have been silenced and suppressed and in addition, understand the cultural diversity and behavior of different cultural groups.

Within society (Ibid: 167-168). In such an emancipatory and democratic process, the community of learners and researchers from different cultural groups are involved in dialogic pedagogy and thus can become activist citizens, challenging the inequality between them and the social world around them (Freire & Macedo, 1998). Freire further argues that the academy has a duty to develop knowledge designed to inspire among the community of learners and researchers itself and an internal force that enables them, on the one hand, to learn different forms of oppression and to become even more aware of the causes and circumstances of oppression. On the other hand, to fight and struggle under the conditions of their oppression (Malaney, 2006: 7). The knowledge imparted by higher education is perceived as having the characteristic power in that it strengthens the critical consciousness of the learning community and enables them to reveal the latent and hidden interests of political and economic hegemony within society. Accordingly, Freire emphasizes the moral commitment of higher education institutions to develop among the learning community the knowledge and skills necessary for social activism that can realize change and emphasize difference. Institutions of higher education have a duty to act for the establishment of a humanistic and moral society, to play an important role in the realization of a transformation of the oppressive reality and in general, in creating a better world (Rocha, 2006: 7). The academy, as implied by Freire, must change its purpose, the nature of its mission and the nature of the slogan that advocates it in a way that is expressed both in its structure and function, so that it must be an integral part of the community and flavor its commitment to it.

Universities, Freire argues, are explicitly designed to train the learning community for active, democratic, and just citizenship, and to make them more partners and involved in community life. The academy and the community of learners and researchers, must show commitment and over-responsibility for the rehabilitation and reorganization of society (Biren, 2003: 185). The academy has a moral obligation to develop social responsibility among the learning community, and to train them to be citizens involved in designing a curriculum that meets the real needs of society through active involvement. This approach, according to Freire, encourages the learning community to analyze various social issues and dilemmas, enables them to be involved in attempts to solve them and strives for the realization of transformation and social justice (Daniels, 2007: 4). Freire repeatedly emphasizes the importance of the academy's involvement in social life and argues that the academy has a human commitment and that is, training the learning community for active activity in community life which is a bridge to active citizenship. In order to realize the principle of democracy in its authentic essence, higher education is committed to training the learning community to take part in public democracy and even to shape a civic leadership with typical abilities and talents against the oppressive reality and for a just and egalitarian reality.

Accordingly, higher education is seen as a means of promoting social and community responsibility, making democratic decisions and shaping the democratic state. Freire's remarks emphasize to us a characteristic aspect of the role of academia and its commitment to the community and society: a moral-humanist aspect that is supposed to foster and develop a civic democratic leadership, with unique abilities and talents, that has the power to understand and respond to social and human dilemmas, and work to promote unique activities that challenge the inequality and conflict that exists within society. Hence, Freire attaches great importance to higher education as being a necessary means of instilling an elementary democratic morality. The commitment of higher education institutions is reflected in the cultivation of mass democratic morality, and the impartation of democratic values as a necessary condition for the continuity of democratic society. The role of these institutions is to produce responsible and democratic citizens.

The acquired knowledge and the creation of the new knowledge in academia should serve, above all, the needs of democracy, and to ensure its continuity. Academy has a moral and humanistic commitment that is reflected in the strengthening of critical consciousness among the learning community and the shaping of insight and rationalism towards a capable civic leadership to produce a just and democratic social order (Jeyaraj, 2014: 19-20). In this context, Freire argues that critical involvement is a necessary condition for democratic education. Therefore, he attaches great importance to the issue of curricula in academia and emphasizes that the curriculum must empower the learning community in order to understand the forces that influence the existing reality. The curriculum, from Freire's point of view, must promote academic freedom, encourage involvement in democratic processes, encourage dialogue, critique and resistance in order to realization social and democratic justice (Malaney, 2006: 11).

Out of these, the fact stands out that higher education institutions are perceived as the mouthpiece of democracy whose role is to criticize the social, political, cultural and economic processes that influence the continued existence of democratic society. These institutions are not affected by global processes and are designed to maintain a balanced and reformed society. These institutions do not serve the political and economic interests of one particular group or another but rather, they are meant to serve the "general good" and strive to ensure the continued existence of a humanistic moral society, which draws from the values of democracy and its authentic foundations.

In conclusion, higher education, from Freire's point of view, is seen as the mouthpiece of democracy, whose role is to criticize the social, political, cultural and economic processes that influence the continued existence of

democratic society. Higher education is supposed to serve the "general good" and strive to ensure the continued existence of a humanistic moral society, which draws on the values of democracy and its authentic foundations. Freire's critical pedagogy Denies the perception that humanis the product of political, social and economic reproduction and emphasizes that human is a creature of research who has the ability to critically examine the world, and to expose the mechanisms of oppression and manipulation used by the dominant hegemony to realize its political, social, cultural and economic interests. According to Ferreira, the investigation and learning of reality, is perceived as a human act that allows a person to strengthen his reason, rationale and critical consciousness. Higher education is committed to training critical intellectuals and strengthening critical awareness among learners and giving them the opportunity not only to question and explore the existing status quo only, but to influence the shaping of the world and the existing reality and to work for an overall social transformation. Freire sees dialogue as a tool for the transformation of consciousness and reality, with dialogue evolving from a democratic discourse as a goal, to a democratic discourse as a means of transforming those involved in it, which allows them to challenge the unequal reality and in general, to produce a more humane fair reality. Accordingly, the institutions of higher education have a duty to work for the creating of a humanistic and moral society, to play an important role in the realization of a transformation of the unequal reality and in general, in creating a better world.

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Author Information

Younis Fareed Abu Alhaija,
Department of Education,
Sakhnin College, Academic College for Teacher
Education, Israel
